

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR MODELING THE WAYS OF PRESENTING INFORMATION IN THE ENGLISH-LANGUAGE NEWS DISCOURSE

Xusanova Zuhra Almamat qizi

e-mail: zuxra.xusanova94@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7107637>

Abstract: The scientific article is based on the rules of cognitive linguistics, media-discourse studies, the communicative style of the English language and is devoted to the study of the specific features of the presentation of the event in the English text of the news report.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, media-discourse studies, the concept of "representation of the event in mass media".

Introduction

It is necessary to follow the rules of cognitive linguistics, speech sciences and the communicative style of the English language when studying the specific features of the presentation of the event in the English text of the news report.

The relevance of the topic is related to the significant impact of nominative and discursive information technologies in the English language on the strategies and methods of presenting news in the world media space, the need to expand knowledge about the cognitive and discursive properties of information. Organization of news text in English-language electronic media consists of clarifying the methodology of cognitive-semantic modeling of the news event using the English language.

The scientific novelty of the scientific article is to reveal the meaning of the concept of "representation of the event in the mass media", to systematically describe the communicative-functional and social-pragmatic specificity of the information content of the English-language mass media. The thematic organization of news text is examined for the first time in a representative corpus of English news material using the nominative density measurement method of the thesaurus. Based on the developed methodology of the cognitive-discursive reconstruction of the news event, the correlation between the categorical-semantic model of the news message and alternative text implementations, the genre-compositional organization of the news text in English was determined.

The practical value of the research results is due to the possibility of using its results in teaching university courses in English stylistics, discourse theory, text processing technology, special courses for journalists and public relations

specialists. The proposed complex method of cognitive-discursive analysis of the corpus of English-language news texts can be used to expand the tools of linguistic monitoring in online journalism, improve the quality of the text content of media resources.

The theoretical significance of the work is in clarifying the rules of discursive linguistics and functional stylistics of the English language to the specific characteristics of the relationship between the ontological image of the event and the linguo-stylistic image in the media discourse; establish a relationship between communicative-pragmatic tasks and genre forms of news speech in English; Proving the position of accuracy, credibility, attractiveness, focus in English news discourse as a linguistically proven tactic of media coverage of an event.

The following proposal is put forward as a scientific hypothesis: media representation is a type of strategy for providing information about an event of social importance, and its cognitive-discursive construction in English-language electronic media is the pragmatic tasks of news journalism. is determined by The accuracy, reliability, attractiveness and focus of the discursive tactic of the news message text are used to reflect the event. They get a specific cognitive-semantic image and functional-stylistic expression through the English language.

Achieving this goal required solving the following tasks:

1) to clarify the ontological, communicative, functional and socio-pragmatic specifics of the information content of the mass media discourse;

2) to determine the content of the concept of "media representation" and clarify the genre and compositional features of the presentation of the event in the English-language mass media discourse;

3) substantiate the criteria for highlighting the informative and discursive characteristics of a news message in the English-language mass media discourse;

4) present a cognitive-discursive model of a news message and identify options for its media representation on the example of a minicorpus of English-language news texts with the tag "Natural disaster"; 5) establish the categorical-semantic features of the media representation of the event in the thesaurus of the minicorpus of English-language news texts with the tag "Natural disaster";

In the results of the scientific article, the following proposals were put forward: media presentation is a type of strategy for providing information about an event of social importance, and its cognitive-discursive construction in English-language electronic media is a pragmatic task of news journalism.

Conclusion

The news message, which has received a specific cognitive-semantic image and functional-stylistic expression in English, is carried out with accuracy, reliability, attractiveness and discursive tactics in the focus. The purpose of the scientific article is a cognitive-discursive and categorical-semantic description of a socially significant event in modern English media discourse.

References:

1. Алексеевна. -Волгоград, 2013. - 18 с. 1. Агапова, А.Н. Заголовок в современной русской прессе: эпистемический и прагматический аспекты [Текст] : автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук: 10.02.01 / Агапова Анастасия Николаевна. - Волгоград, 2011. - 23 с.
2. Александрова, Е.С. Гендерная маркированность англоязычного новостного текста: на материале современной британской прессы [Текст] : дис. ... канд. филол. наук: 10.02.04 / Александрова Елена Сергеевна. - Волгоград, 2007. - 182 с.
3. Александрова, О.В. Язык средств массовой информации как часть коллективного пространства общества [Текст] / О.В. Александрова // Язык СМИ как объект междисциплинарного исследования / Под ред. М.Н. Володиной- М.: Изд-во МГУ, 2003. - С. 89 - 99.
4. Алещанова, И.В. Газетный текст как разновидность массово-информационного дискурса [Текст] / И.В. Алещанова // Языковая личность: институциональный и персональный дискурс: сб. науч. тр. / под ред. В.И. Карасика, Г.Г. Слышкина. - Волгоград: Перемена, 2000. - С. 131 - 140.
5. Амзин, А.А. Новостная интернет - журналистика. Учебное пособие 2-е изд., испр. и доп. [Текст] / А.А. Амзин. - М.: Аспект Пресс, 2012. - 144 с.
6. Андрющенко, Е.А. Репрезентация образа «чужого» в англоязычном медиадискурсе (на материале британских СМИ) [Текст] : автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук : 10.02.04 / Андрющенко Екатерина